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The Rights Of Vulnerable Children During Armed Conflicts; The Case Of The Nigerian Civil War

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ABSTRACT

Human rights are inalienable rights and these rights are clearly provided for in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)¹ Children represent the continuity of life in human existence. Without them, there is no future for mankind. From time immemorial, children have been victims of one form of exploitation or the other. They have often times become the conscious targets and victims of armed conflict. On the international political scene, the protection of children in armed conflict has continued to gain wider attention. For instance, the Security Council² which is a major organ of the United Nations has a special working group which pays special attention to the most serious violations of children's rights in armed conflict every year. The activities of the group include reports on the recruitment and use of children as child soldiers, maiming of children, education, attacks on schools and hospitals, sexual violence, rape and the denial of humanitarian access by parties to armed conflict. This to a great extent places or classifies children as vulnerable persons whenever there are hostilities whether between States or involving the State and terrorist organizations. That is not to say that the Child or Children are the only vulnerable species during terrorism and counter terrorism operations, but only one of such class of persons whose rights are trampled or totally violated during armed conflicts as the rights of women and other groups or set of persons equally suffer the same fate as the Child or Children during armed conflict occasioned by the Nigerian civil war in 1967 or any other armed conflict.

Keywords: children's rights, conflict, terrorism, Nigerian civil war

INTRODUCTION

Notwithstanding the plethora of international human right and humanitarian law provisions for the protection of children in armed conflict, the reality is that children are still victims of violations of their rights which are protected under international law. For instance, in 2011, a report from the office of the United Nations Secretary-General contains a record of ongoing and new violation of the rights of children. In 15 of the 22 areas covered in the report, schools were targeted by armed forces and armed groups, this includes forced recruitment of children and closure of schools. In Afghanistan for instance, the solders compelled the dancing boys known as *bacchabaazi* to dance at parties and they also abuse them sexually. In Iraq, al-Qaida compel children to carry out suicide bombings³. They call the children "birds of paradise". In Nigeria, Boko Haram has continued to use children for suicide bombing attacks. There are still other reports that show that children face very high levels of victimization from armed forces and armed groups⁴. It is thus evident that despite the array of international instruments made to protect children in armed conflict, atrocities and wickedness committed against children during armed conflict cannot be imagined.

¹ Ss. 33, 34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42 and 43 CFRN 1999

²UN Security Council Resolution 1998 (2011), UN Document S/RES/1988(2011), 12 July, 2011

³General Assembly/Security council, *Children and Armed Conflict: Report of the Secretary General*, UN Document A/65/820-5/2011/250, 23rd April 2011.

⁴Human Right Council, *Human Rights in Palestine and other Occupied Arab Territories: Report of the United Nations Fact Finding Mission on the Gaza Conflict*. UN document A/HRC/12/48, 25th December, 2009.

Before the adoption of the various international instruments for the protection of children in armed conflict, the protection of children during armed conflicts depended on the socio-cultural perceptions of the armed forces or groups. Essentially, the armed forces or group relied on their conscience and the protection for the children depended on the size of the soldier's conscience and his socio-cultural beliefs. Two girls wrote memoirs about their armed service during World War I. The stories of their mobilization are similar: Both Marina Yurlova and Sofia Nowosielska were 14 years when war was declared in 1914, and both came from patriotic, well-to-do families; their fathers were mobilized immediately and both were eager to follow the men. Their autobiographies trace the confusion in which they followed the troops and became integrated into military units. Their exploits, wounds and survival through the upheavals marked the end of the War in both Russia and Poland⁵.

Article 1 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) defined children as people who are under the age of 18 years. The voice of children was aptly captured by Human Rights Watch⁶, where a 15 year old girl Minova South Kivu had this to say:

I was just coming back from the river to fetch water... Two soldiers came up to me and told me that if I refuse to sleep with them, they will kill me. They beat me and ripped my clothes. One of the soldiers raped me... My parents spoke to a commander and he said that his soldiers do not rape, and that I am lying. I recognized the two soldiers and I know that one of them is called Edouard.⁷

It appears that some of the problems child victims of armed conflict face are not properly understood by the persons whose duties are to protect children from armed conflict. Children have been taken as slaves for sexual and economic gains of the victors. Children have been armed to defend the blocks of the victor from enemy groups; children have been given to warriors to be their assistants. For instance, in European military, history a boy could become a knight's page at the age of seven and receive combat training at that age. At the age of 13 or 14, he would graduate to a junior position on the battlefield itself.⁸

Even when these problems were known and seemed to be appreciated, the response of the international community to the protection of children in armed conflict were not enough and consequently did not address the challenges. In the 20th century, when it was discovered that most boys and girls were innocent victims of warfare and that they needed food aid and other assistance, the response of the international community was to launch agencies such as Save the Children (as a response to the sufferings of children living under the economic sanctions of World War I in Germany); Plan International (which was a response to the dangers faced by children during the Spanish Civil War in 1937), Oxfam (which was launched as a response to the deprivation facing Greek children in 1942) and UNICEF (which was established in 1946 to provide emergency food and health care to children in post-World War II Europe). The family reunification efforts of the International Committee of the Red Cross after World War II was also seen as a protection for the innocent victims of armed conflict.

In 1996, Graca Machel released a report on the impact of armed conflict on children⁹. The report triggered greater attention to children living in armed conflict situation. This led to some progress on protective standards. Sadly, those protective standards are very difficult if not impossible to enforce in times of conflict and consequently did not make any improvement on the lives of children in armed conflict. UNICEF estimated that more than one billion boys and girls live in countries or territories affected by armed conflict and out of these number, about 300 million are under five years old¹⁰.

⁵Civil Soldiers in World War I: Marina Yurlova and Sofia Nowosielska by Margaret R. Hogonnet. In *Children and Armed Conflict: Cross Disciplinary Investigations*, edited by Daniel Thomas Cook and John Wall at Page 7.

⁶Human Rights Watch, *Dr. Congo: Hold Army commander Responsible for Rapes*, 2009.<<http://www.hrw.org/en/news/2009/07/16/dr.congo-hold-army-commanders-responsible-rapes>> accessed 20 January 2025

⁷ Human Rights Watch, *Dr. Congo: Hold Army commander Responsible for Rapes*, 2009.<<http://www.hrw.org/en/news/2009/07/16/dr.congo-hold-army-commanders-responsible-rapes>> accessed 20 January 2025

⁸David Rosen, *Child Soldiers: Victims or Heroes*”, in FDU magazine, summer/fall 2005, <<http://www.fdu.edu/newspubs/magazine/05sf/childrensoldiers.html>> accessed 20 January 2025

⁹United Nations and UNICEF, “impact of armed conflict on children”, New York, 1996< <http://www.UNICEF.org/Graca/>> accessed 20 March 2025

¹⁰UNICEF, *Progress for Children*, 2009. 20 < [http://www.Unicef.org/protection/files/progress_for_children.No.8EN080309\(1\).Pdf](http://www.Unicef.org/protection/files/progress_for_children.No.8EN080309(1).Pdf)> accessed 13 March 2025

The report of the Office of the UN Secretary General shows that 53 parties in situations of armed conflict (both state and non-state actors) committed grave violations against children including killing, maiming, the recruitment and use of children as soldiers, abduction, rape and other sexual violence, attacks on school and hospitals as well as barring humanitarian access in 2008.¹¹ There is evidence in that report that children are specifically targeted for atrocities in order to demoralize or terrorize opponents and there is no regard for their lives and well-being as landmines, cluster bombs and other weapons were used and the boys and girls were used as shields¹².

Indeed, the sufferings and challenges of children in armed conflict are so much devastating. Children are still used as suicide bombers in Sri Lanka, Afghanistan, Palestine, Iraq and Nigeria. In 2008 and 2009, the United Nations Country Operative in Iraq documented that three children detonated themselves, six children were in training as suicide bombers and one girl was intercepted while she wore explosives¹³.

Who is a child?

The definition of 'child' and its conception have been largely coloured by the definer's discipline, school of thought as well as time. This explains why there are biological, social and legal definitions of the child and different conception of the child across time. Biologically a child is a person between birth and puberty or in the developmental stage, between infancy and adulthood. From the 16th century to modern era, society began to treat and relate to the child not as a 'miniature adult', but as a person of a lower level of maturity needing adult protection, love and nurturing; unlike the in Middle Ages when children were portrayed as 'miniature adults', with no childish characteristics. Legally, the definition of a child also differs across space and time.

The Canadian Supreme Court in *Ogg-Moss v. R*¹⁴ held that:

Both in common parlance and as a legal concept the term 'child' has two primary meanings. One refers to chronological age and is the converse of the term 'adult'; the other refers to the lineage and is reciprocal of the term parent. A child in the first sense was defined at common law as a person under the age of fourteen. This definition may be modified by statutory provision... No statutory modification however, fixes an age higher than the age of majority.... A child in the second sense was defined at common law the legitimate offspring of a parent, but in most jurisdictions, this definition has been amended by statute to constitute all offspring, whether legitimate or not as the children of their natural or adoptive parents.¹⁵

In that connection, Article 1 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989 defines a child as "every human being below the age of eighteen years unless, under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier". This definition fixes the age of majority at 18 subject to other laws applicable to the child in a given circumstance. Similarly the African Charter on the Right and Welfare of the African Child, 1990 defines a child as "every human being below the age of 18 years." Nigeria has also similarly defined a "child" as such. Thus, in the Nigerian Child Rights Act, 2003, a person who has not attained the age of 18 is a child¹⁶.

While every one presumes that they know what childhood is and who children are, the concept of childhood is however not as easy as it appears. It is a rather very complex social contract of which any attempt to define and demarcate it is inevitably artificial¹⁷. It is on the basis of the new perception of children as worthy of care and special protection, that the international community has paid keen attention on the protection of children, especially in situations of armed conflict. But what really is armed conflict?

¹¹UN Secretary General, *Children and armed conflicts*, Reports of the Secretary General", A/63/785-3/200958. UN, 2009, 47 <[http://daccess-ods.un.org/access.nsf/get? Open & Ds= A/63/785 & Lang=E & Area= UNDOC](http://daccess-ods.un.org/access.nsf/get?Open+Ds=A/63/785+Lang=E+Area=UNDOC)> accessed 17 March 2025

¹²UNICEF and No Peace Without Justice, *International Criminal Justice and Children*, Innocent Research Centre, 2002, 30, <<http://www.UNICEF.org/emerg/files/ICJC.pdf>> accessed 13 July 2025

¹³Office of the Special Representative On Children And Armed Conflict <<http://ww.un.org/children/conflict/English/conflicts.html>> accessed 10 November 2025

¹⁴(1984) 2 SCR 173

¹⁵ *Ogg-Moss v. R* (1984) 2 SCR 173

¹⁶ Child Right Act, 2003, S. 277

¹⁷G. Bueren, *International law on the rights of the child*, (RJR Levesque 1995) 32

The concept of armed conflict

Prior to the emergence of the concept of “armed conflict” as it is known today, the prevailing term was “war”, which was basically defined as a state of belligerency between sovereigns. Thus, Lauterpacht, defined war as a “contestation between two or more States through their armed forces, for the purpose of overpowering each other and imposing such conditions of peace as the victor pleases”¹⁸. The word “war” was thus a term reminiscent of the League of Nations and was used only once in the Preamble United Nations Charter. Thus, since the adoption of the UN Charter in 1945, the concept of “armed conflict” has been used in international instruments, writings, text-books and international case law.

In fact the Geneva Conventions on the Protection of Victims of War of 1949 (and Additional Protocols I and II of 1977), the 1954 Hague Convention for the Protection Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict and the Convention on Diplomatic Relations, 1961, all made use of the term “armed conflict”. It has been argued that the concept of “armed conflict” is much broader than the traditional concept of war because, the term “armed conflict” embraces not only the use of force in a warlike manner between states (whether or not the parties see themselves as being in war) and all military measures short of war, but also wars of national liberation¹⁹. Be that as it may though, there is no universally acceptable definition of armed conflict. Generally, armed conflict has been defined as “the use of armed force by one or more states (international armed conflict) or between one or more armed groups against their own government or between armed groups themselves (internal conflict)²⁰. The International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) in the *Prosecutor v. DuskoTadic*²¹ held that

*Armed conflict exists whenever there is a resort to armed force between States or protracted violence between governmental authorities and organized armed groups or between such groups within a State. International humanitarian law applies from the initiation of such armed conflicts and extends beyond the cessation of hostilities until a general conclusion of peace is reached; or, in the case of internal conflicts, a peaceful settlement is achieved. Until that moment, international humanitarian law continues to apply in the whole territory of the warring States or, in the case of internal conflicts, the whole territory under the control of a party, whether or not actual combat takes place there.*²²

While this definition has been adopted by other international bodies, it is however vital to note that the definition is limited to international armed conflict and does not seem to embrace armed conflicts that do not involve two or more state parties. To distinguish an armed conflict from other types of international or internal disturbances or tensions, the hostilities must reach a high degree of intensity. Thus, international humanitarian law distinguishes between two types of armed conflict:

- a. **International armed conflict:** This involves resort to armed force between two or more states international armed conflict encompasses any use of force or arms between two or more states (belligerents), irrespective of the intensity of the armed conflict²³; and
- b. **Non-international armed conflict:** Protracted armed confrontations occurring between governmental armed forces and the forces of one or more armed groups or between such groups arising in the territory of a state.

However, for the armed confrontation between the parties qualify as armed conflict, it must reach a minimum level of intensity and the parties involved in the conflict must show a minimum of organization. In the light of the foregoing therefore, while the conflict between the US and Iraq in 2003 would qualify as an international armed conflict, the conflict between Nigeria and Biafra, the Niger Delta militancy and the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria are examples of non-international armed conflicts.

¹⁸H. Lauterpacht, (Ed.). *International Law: A Treatise by L. Oppenheim*. New York: David McKay Co. Vol. II: Disputes, War and Neutrality, 1952. 202

¹⁹ K. J. Partch, Armed Conflict, in R. Bernhardt, (1990)(1) *Encyclopedia of Public International Law*, 251.

²⁰ Josef Mrazek, *Armed Conflicts and the Use of Force*, CYIL (2010).

²¹ (1995) 17-94-1 A

²² *Prosecutor V DuskoTadic* (1995) 17-94-1 A, para 70

²³ *Prosecutor .v. Lubanga Dyilo*, ICC-01/04-01/06, 539

Effects of armed conflicts on children

In recent times, the nature of armed conflict has changed from conventional warfare which take place in isolated battlefields. The vast majority of contemporary armed conflict not only take place within the territory of a specific country, but also focus on political, economic, social and psychological disruption of a country. In this new form of armed conflict, civilians are always caught in the midst of the battle and routinely made targets. These kinds of armed conflict have been noted to have both direct and indirect effects on the population generally, but also children specifically. Scholars and expert have noted the following to be the effect of armed conflict on children:

Child mortality and morbidity: Children usually account for the majority of civilian casualties during armed conflicts. In 1995, Plunkett and Southall²⁴ noted that about “2,000,000 children have died in war zones in the last ten years. This does not represent the number for whom the end, through sudden and unexpected, is quick and painful as with those caught out while playing, discriminately by the sniper’s bullet or indiscriminately by the stray mortar, or killed in the night with the rest of the village by the advancing every”. It has been observed that more than 2.7 million children died in the Democratic Republic of Congo as a result of the conflict and majority of these deaths do not occur from weapons themselves, but from preventable diseases that are not prevented or treated because the health systems and infrastructure have been destroyed. Thus, during armed conflicts, not only are large numbers of children killed and injured, but also countless others grow up deprived of their material and emotional need including the structures that give meaning to social and cultural life.²⁵

Child abuse: Amidst armed conflict, children are usually subjected to physical, sexual and emotional and other kinds of abuses. Reports from different parts of the world monitoring armed conflicts show most evidently that children in armed conflict are unfortunate victims of sexual and other kinds of abuses by various parties to the conflict. Armed groups are known to use sexual abuses to control communities, and girls are used as “booty” to motivate soldiers. Sexual violence has been directly linked with girls’ recruitment and use by armed groups, where they frequently serve as sex-mates or “wives” to commanders and soldiers. In the groups, they are forced to use methods of contraception that are inadequate and harmful to their health. According to Watchlist, “Girls are held under false promises of safety, money and glory to evade domestic violence, poverty, or other problems at home, and at times recruited by force. Once they have joined the armed group, there is no going back”. Children also face different kinds of abuses in refugee camps ranging from violence and discrimination to harassment²⁶.

Loss of adult protection: It was observed that in 1995, over one million children had been or displaced as a result of armed conflict²⁷. Thus, during armed conflicts children lose access to the care, empathy and attention of adult who love them. Armed conflicts, the loss of parents, the separation from parents, parents’ extreme pre-occupation with protecting and finding subsistence for the family and the emotional liability of distressed or distracted parent, lead to significant and frequent disruption in their attachments. Indeed, more often than not, children in armed conflict lose adult protection that is needed for their wellbeing and safety.

Use of children as soldiers: There is uncontroverted evidence that across the world, children are regularly recruited and used as soldiers in armed conflict. Watchlist differentiates the “recruitment” (forced or voluntary enlistment or conscription into any kind of armed force or group) from “use”(employing their services as cooks, partners, messengers, spies, and collaborators) of children in armed conflict. Whether by means of direct or indirect involvement in armed conflict, armed conflict robs the individual of childhood. It brutalizes children and diminishes their value as individuals. It creates the risk of abuse, physical and sexual. Paradoxically, the child holding a Kalashnikov is easier to kill or rape than a child playing football or sitting in a classroom²⁸.

Psychological trauma: Researchers have shown that the psychological effect of armed conflict on children ranges from aggression and revenge to anxiety, fear, grief and depression. Purwar, Dhabaland Chakravarty²⁹ have categorized the psychological effects of armed conflict and children as

²⁴ Plunkett, M.C.B & Southall, D. P, *The Effects of War on Children* (6th Edn *Current Paediatrics*, 1996) 211-218.

²⁵ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, *The Impact and Effects of War on Children*, 2013.

²⁶ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, *supra*, p 3.

²⁷ Plunkett, M.C.B & Southall, D. P, *The Effects of War on Children* (6th Edn *Current Paediatrics*, 1996) 214.

²⁸ Plunkett, M.C.B & Southall, D. P, *The Effects of War on Children* (6th Edn *Current Paediatrics*, 1996) 214.

²⁹ AnirudhPurwar ,ArnabDhabal&DiptarkaChakravarty , *Psychological Effects of War and Terrorism on Children* , 2004.

dependent on the age of the child. The horror and trauma associated with untimely death and destruction, severe injuries and starvation due to war. Some children later in life exhibit or imitate the violence from the war.

Disruption of home, schooling and health care system: Warfare and or armed conflict generally disrupts a child's home environment which makes them refugees or internally displaced persons. The UNCHR observed that children below 18 years constituted more than 50% of the refugee population globally, the highest figure in a decade. The same as time of schooling as it has been demonstrated repeatedly that armed conflicts have disastrous and devastating effect on child education. It has however been shown that with resilience, a child can recover and do well academically despite the setbacks of the conflict.

The protection of children in armed conflict under the Geneva Convention IV, 1949 and its protocols

The Second World War saw millions of civilians and children as its unfortunate victims. Reports and experience during the War showed most evidently that there was an overarching need to draw up international instruments that will not only limit the means and methods of warfare, but also protect persons who are not part of the armed hostilities. This led to the adoption of four Geneva Conventions: Geneva Convention I, II, III and IV. Geneva Convention I concerns the treatment and protection of members of the armed forces who are wounded and sick in the field; Geneva Convention II, regulates the treatment and protection of members of the armed forces who are shipwrecked or wounded and sick at sea; Geneva Convention III makes provision for the treatment of prisoners of war; and Geneva Convention IV deals with the freedom and prosecution of critical persons in times of war, occupation or internment.

Geneva Convention IV, 1949 (hereinafter, GCIV) has been generally described as the first international treaty to afford protection to children during armed conflict. Thus, Articles 17, 23, 24, 25, 27, 38, 50, 76, 81, 82, 89, 94, and 136 amongst others make provisions that afford protection to children in various ways:

Protection of children against the effects of hostilities: The Convention protects children from the effects of armed conflict in that under Article 41, children who have not attained the age of 15 years and mothers of children under seven years are classified under civilian population who can be received into hospitals and safe zones so as to protect them from the effects of conflict. Similarly, parties to conflict are under duties to ensure "the removal from besieged or encircled areas, of wounded, sick, infirm and aged persons, *children* and maternity cases..."³⁰

Care and aid for children: Under the GCIV, contracting parties to the Convention are under duty to "permit the free passage of all consignments of essential foodstuffs, clothing, and medicines intended for *children* under fifteen, expectant mothers and maternity cases"³¹. Where a territory is under occupation, the occupying power is under duty to "facilitate the proper working of all institutions devoted to the care and education of *children*"³². This implies that an occupying power is barred from destroying or stifling institutions, established for the care of children during armed conflict. In the same spirit of the care for the child, the GCIV provides that parties to a conflict must make provision for the dependents of internees, especially where such "dependents are without adequate means for support or are unable to earn a living"³³, which is typical of children, especially during armed conflict.

The child and his family: The Geneva Convention IV proceeds on the understanding that the family is critical for the survival, protection and nurturance of a child. Same is the case during armed conflict. Thus, where members of a family are under internment, "members of the same family, and in particular parents and *children* shall be lodged together in the same place of internment, except when separation of a temporary nature is necessitated for reasons of employment or health...internees may request that their children who are left at liberty without parental case be interned with them"³⁴. In the same vein, protecting the family ties of child, Article 50 prohibits the change of the family or personal status of children, while Article 51 prohibits compelling a child under 18 years to work.

³⁰ GCIV A. 17

³¹ Article 23, GCIV

³² Article 50, GCIV

³³ Article 81, GCIV

³⁴ Article 82, GCIV

Identification of children: To protect children from abandonment during armed conflict, Article 24 of the GCIV makes provision for the identification for children under 12 years by wearing an identity disc.

The Convention generally made provisions for the education of the child³⁵; upholding the personal and family tree of the child³⁶; giving children preferential treatment much like the citizens of the state concerned³⁷; prohibits the imposition of death penalty on a child during armed conflict³⁸, amongst others. Indeed, the Geneva Convention IV afforded a measure of protection of children in armed conflict for the first time in human history. In fact, it used the word “children” about 22 times and made indirect reference to children about 17 times. That such provisions were made for the protection of children as at 1949 “show that, already in 1949, it was felt that children should be specially protected against warfare”³⁹.

Nevertheless, scholars, experts and researchers have pointed out the inherent weakness of Geneva Convention IV in terms of protection of children. In the first place, it has been argued that the Convention is mainly concerned with the treatment those who are victims of armed conflict generally and as such provided “limited protection for children in armed conflict”⁴⁰. Carolyn Hamilton argued that though the Convention purports to protect “victims” of armed conflict, who are vulnerable, the Convention’s definitions of victimhood is narrowly defined in that it does not cover all civilians affected by armed conflicts, and the Convention only seeks to protect civilians who have fallen into the hands of the enemy, and as such does not protect from the conduct of hostilities itself. The author also noted that while “there are some articles which relate to children, but once again, the protection afforded is not particularly powerful”⁴¹.

Given the foregoing inherent shortcomings of the Fourth Geneva Convention, the emergence of new kinds of warfare after the Second World War, the sophistication of the means and methods of warfare and their consequent severe loss of civilian lives including that of children beckoned on international humanitarian law to respond to the changes. Hence, after a long period of negotiation which started in 1968, a Diplomatic Conference was held from 1974-1977 whose aim was to supplement and develop international humanitarian law taking into accounts, the needs of the time, in terms of armed conflicts. This gave birth to the Two Additional Protocols I and II, 1977 to the Geneva Convention IV, 1949. The prime aim of these protocols according to Hamilton was:

[t]o strengthen humanitarian law in the light of the experience of the Vietnam war, the use of new weapons of war and the extensive suffering of civilians in contemporary armed conflict, particularly those fought in the name of self-determination.⁴²

While the Geneva Convention afforded “general protection” to children as members of the civilian population⁴³, the Additional Protocol I⁴⁴ however not only made provision for children’s “special protection” during armed conflict, but also laid down the principle of the said special protection in Article 77 thus:

Children shall be the object of *special respect* and shall be *protected* against any form of indecent assault. The parties to the conflict shall provide them with the care and they require; whether because of their age or for any other reason⁴⁵.

³⁵Article 50, 94, GCIV

³⁶ Articles 27 and 50, GCIV

³⁷ Article 38(5);

³⁸ Article 24, GCIV

³⁹ Demise Plattner (1984). Protection of children in international humanitarian law. (2009)(240) *International Review of the Red Cross* 30

⁴⁰ International Bureau for Children’s Rights (2010) *Children and armed conflict: A guide for international humanitarian and human rights law*, 77.

⁴¹ C Hamilton (2001) ‘Armed Conflict: The protection of children under international law’ (2001) (2) *The international journal of Children’s Rights* 56

⁴²C Hamilton (2001) ‘Armed Conflict: The protection of children under international law’ (2001) (2) *The international journal of Children’s Rights* 56

⁴³ Demise Plattner,

⁴⁴ C Hamilton (2001) ‘Armed Conflict: The protection of children under international law’ (2001) (2) *The international journal of Children’s Rights* 59

⁴⁵ C Hamilton (2001) ‘Armed Conflict: The protection of children under international law’ (2001) (2) *The international journal of Children’s Rights* 59

While the Additional Protocol I is made to apply exclusively to international armed conflict, the principle of *special protection* for children during armed conflict also applies to children in situation of non-international armed conflict⁴⁶. Importantly, Additional Protocol I set the minimum age for the recruitment into the armed forces and for direct participation of children in armed conflict at 15 years of age. This marked the first time that the issue of children being associated with an armed group/forces was specifically dealt with under a binding international treaty. Thus Protocol I to the GCIV broadened the scope of protection afforded children and prohibited the direct participation of children under 15 years of age in armed conflict.

Given that majority of warfare or armed conflict in the latter part of the 20th century and 21st century are principally internal or non-international conflict, whereas Protocol I is limited to international armed conflict, the question arose as to how children can be protected in situations of non-international armed conflict. This was readily answered by Additional Protocol II relating to Victims of Non-international Armed Conflict. This was the first binding international document to directly address the conduct of parties in non-international armed conflict. While Protocol II upheld most of the special protection principles under protocol 1, it however provided that children must be protected from recruitment by both government and armed opposition groups during such conflict.

A community examination of the provisions of Geneva Convention IV and its additional Protocols II and II shows that under international humanitarian law, children are afforded the following protection:

- a. **General protection:** during international armed conflict, children who are not taking part in same are protected by the provisions of GCIV and the Protocols particularly with respect to right to life, prohibition on coercion, corporal punishment, torture, collective punishment and reprisals⁴⁷ and the rule that parties to an armed conflict must distinguish between combatants and civilians (inclusive of children) and must not attack civilians deliberately⁴⁸. However, when it comes to non-international armed conflicts, children are also protected as persons not taking direct part in the hostilities pursuant to the provisions of the GCIV⁴⁹ and as the general civilian population⁵⁰ who must not be attacked during armed conflicts.
- b. **Special protection:** while the Geneva Convention recognized the need to afford children a measure of protection as members of the civilian population during armed conflicts, it was Protocol I to GCIV however that in its Article 77, laid down the principle of *special protection* which has been extended to non-international armed conflicts⁵¹. The specific/special protection to children in armed conflict under these instruments has been summarized⁵² as follows;
 - i. Evacuation, special zones⁵³;
 - ii. Assistance and care⁵⁴;
 - iii. Identification, family reunification and unaccompanied children⁵⁵;
 - iv. Education, cultural environment⁵⁶;
 - v. Arrested, detained and interned children⁵⁷;

⁴⁶ Protocol II to the GCIV, A 4.

⁴⁷ Article 27-34 of the GCIV; Article 75 of Protocol I to the GCIV.

⁴⁸ Article 48 and 51 of Protocol I to the GCIV. See also Article 16 and 49 of the Geneva Convention III relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War which provide that prisoners of war must be treated fairly subject to the age of the specific person. This implies that where children are taken prisoners during armed conflict, the detaining state party is under duty to treat the children fairly.

⁴⁹ See common Article 3 in the Geneva Conventions I, II, III and IV; Article 4 of the Additional Protocol II.

⁵⁰ Article 13 of the Additional Protocol II to the Geneva Conventions IV.

⁵¹ Article 4(3) Additional Protocol II to the GCIV, 1977.

⁵² International Committee of the Red Cross (2003). Legal protection of children in armed conflict. Advisory Service on International Humanitarian Law.

⁵³ Article 14, 17, 24 (2), 49(3), 132(2) of the Geneva Convention IV; Article 78 of the Additional Protocol I; Article 4 (3e) of Additional Protocol II.

⁵⁴ Article 23, 24(1), 38(5), 50 and 89 (5) of the Geneva Convention IV; Articles 70(1), 77(1) of the Additional Protocol I, Article 4 (3) Additional Protocol II;

⁵⁵ Article 24, 25, 26, 49 (3), 50 and 82 of the Geneva Convention IV; Article 74, 75 (5), 76(3) and 78 of the Additional Protocol I; Article 4 (36) and 6 (4) of Additional Protocol II;

⁵⁶ Article 24 (1), 50 and 94 of the Geneva Convention IV; Article 78(2) Additional Protocol I; Article 4 (3a) Additional Protocol II

- vi. Exemption from death penalty⁵⁸;
- vii. Participation in armed conflict⁵⁹.

Thus, whereas, Protocol 1 in its Article 77 (the most important provision vis-à-vis children in armed conflict) made copious and special provisions that protect children during international armed conflict, Article 4 of the Additional Protocol II gave fundamental guarantee to all children in a bid to ensure that they are treated humanely during armed conflict. The protections accorded children under international humanitarian law goes beyond the Geneva Convention IV and its additional protocols, dealing with protection of victims of armed conflict, but also extends to rules governing how warfare and armed conflicts are conducted, such as the use of on conventional weapons in armed conflicts.

International humanitarian law protection of children in armed conflict through regulation of use of weapons

Over and above the reactionary practice of making provisions for the protection of children who are ‘victims’ of armed conflict already, international humanitarian law has also taken the proactive step of regulating how wars are waged and the kind of weapons used having regard to the peculiar circumstances of children. The years following the adoption of the additional protocols (to the Geneva Conventions) 1977 saw the proliferation of conventional weapons that have devastating effects on civilians and children before and after armed conflicts. The proliferation of light weapons has also led to and increased the recruitment of children as child soldiers. It was in response to this that the international community adopted the Convention on Conventional Weapons, 1980⁶⁰.

The instrument protects military officers, civilians and civilian assets from the effect of different weapons as specified under its various five protocols. Protocol II has been amended in 1996 to apply to non-international armed conflicts. Pointedly, the 1980 Protocol II⁶¹ to the Convention on Conventional Weapons in Article 6(1)(b)(v) specifically prohibits the use of body-traps associated with “children’s toys or other portable objects or products specially designed for the feeding, health, hygiene, clothing or education of children”. This is the protection of children, knowing that such devices are dangerous to children.

Over the decades, it has been recognized that landmines – whether anti-personnel or anti-vehicle – remain a threat to people’s lives even years after an armed conflict because of their potentiality to kill or maim indiscriminately anyone who stumbles upon them. It was in response to this that the Mine Ban Treaty was adopted in 1997⁶². Landmines do not distinguish between soldiers and civilians, nor between children and adults. These make landmines particularly dangerous to children because:

- i. they are closer to the centre of the blast and their chances of surviving massive loss of blood are minimal;
- ii. they are often victims of their own curiosity and love of play, something they are eager to resume following the cessation of hostilities. Mines, which come in different shapes, sizes and colours, can be enticing to children;
- iii. children perform jobs that are crucial to the economic survival of the family, such as tending livestock, scavenging, gathering firewood and collecting water. These tasks are often carried out in heavily mined areas;
- iv. and it has become common practice in some areas for children to be paid a small amount of money to retrieve landmines for re-sale.⁶³

It was having regard to the overall deadly effects of the use of landmines in armed conflict that its production, stockpiling and use was prohibited by the convention as well as their destruction

⁵⁷ Article 51 (2), 76 (5) 82, 85 (2), 89, 94 and 119 (2) and 132 of the Geneva Convention IV; Article 77 (3 & 4) of the (3rd) of the Additional Protocol II.

⁵⁸ Article 68 (4) of the Geneva Convention IV; Article 77 (5) of the Additional Protocol I; Article 6 (4) Additional Protocol II.

⁵⁹ Article 77 of the Additional Protocol I and Article 4 (3) of the Additional Protocol II.

⁶⁰ Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May be Deemed to be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects, 1980, amended on the 21st of December, 2001.

⁶¹ 1980 Protocol on the Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Mines, Booby-Traps, and other Devices

⁶² Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and the Transfer of Anti-Personnel Landmines and on their Destruction (1997)154 (also known as the Ottawa Treaty and the Mine Ban Treaty).

⁶³ International Bureau for Children’s Rights, *supra*, p. 81

mandated. This, in the long run, afforded protection to children by ensuring that weapons that have such indiscriminate deadly effects on their lives before and after an armed conflict is completely prohibited from use in armed conflicts.

Charter of the United Nations, 1945

The United Nations was established in 1945. It succeeded the League of Nations which woefully failed to prevent World War I (1914 – 1919) and World War II (1939 – 1945). The purpose of the United Nation is clearly captured in its preamble:

[t]o save succeeding generations from the scourge of war, which twice in our lifetime has brought untold sorrow to mankind, and to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person, in the equal rights of men and women and of nations large and small.⁶⁴

While the Charter is not strictly speaking, a human right creating instrument, it is however founded on core values of human rights as one of the purposes of the United Nations is “promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language or religion”⁶⁵. All members also pledge themselves to take part and separate actions for the achievement of the purposes of the body⁶⁶. Thus, through these provisions, the UN Charter lays foundations for mobilizing international cooperation for respect for human rights of all persons including children, even if “children” is not specifically mentioned in the Charter.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948 (herein, UDHR,) proclaimed rights and freedoms that apply to all persons at all times and places (“universally”). It is founded on the philosophy that the “recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom justice and peace in the world”, and that “disregard and contempt for human rights have resulted in barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind”⁶⁷. The UDHR, building on the Charter of the United Nations, recalled that member states had pledged themselves to achieve, in cooperation with the United Nations, the promotion of universal respect for and observance of human rights and fundamental freedom, made provisions for various civil, political and socio-economic rights which are not only inter-related, but also interdependent. The UDHR, 1948, is the bedrock of fundamental human rights as they are known today across the globe.

Given that the Declaration applies to every one of the human family, the UDHR, therefore applies to children as well. Specifically however, the UDHR, made reference to “children” once. The Article provides that Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection”.⁶⁸ This provision seems to follow the child protectionist model, which holds that children are vulnerable and as such, are entitled to protection and special care from adults.

Similarly, parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children. In view of these provisions, the stage was set for recognition of protection for children under international human rights law and as such states universally have an obligations to not only protect children, but also make provisions for their welfare, care and compulsory education⁶⁹.

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966

This human rights instrument built on the principles of human right proclaimed in the UN Charter and the right granted under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. While the International Covenant on Civil and political Right (ICCPR) in not specifically for children it however has some provisions that concern children.⁷⁰ As a group in the human family, children are also entitled to the civil right

⁶⁴ Preamble to the UN Charter

⁶⁵ UN Charter A. 1(3) and A. 55(c)

⁶⁶ UN Charter A. 56

⁶⁷ Preamble to the UDHR, 1948

⁶⁸ UDHR. A. 25(1)

⁶⁹ UDHR A. 26(1)

⁷⁰ ICCPR 1966 A. 14,18, and 23.

enshrined in the ICCPR. The ICCPR however, makes specific provision for children under Article 24 thus:

Every child shall have, without any discrimination as to race, colour, sex, language, religion, national or social origin, property or birth, the right to such measures of protection as are required by his status as a minor, on the part of his family, society and the state; Every child shall be registered immediately after birth and shall have a name; Every child has the right to acquire a nationality.⁷¹

This provision makes it explicit that the ICCPR also adopts the principle of protection for children. The right to protection also confers a corresponding duty on the family, society and state (caregivers) to uphold children's right to protection. Granted that the ICCPR, allows derogating from some of the right granted therein in situations of emergency⁷² which poses a threat the life of the state, there are some provisions such as the right to life and such rights that cannot be derogated from.

Declarations on the Rights of the Child, 1924 and 1959

The Declaration on the Rights of the Child, adopted on the 26th of September, 1924 by the General Assembly of the League of Nations, is founded on the recognition that "*Mankind owes to the child, the best that it has to give*". Hence, on the basis of the recognition, the child must be given the means for its normal development, cared and catered for when hungry, sick or orphaned and reclaimed when delinquent. The Declaration also states that the child must be the first to receive relief in times of distress which refers to moments of armed conflict. It has been stated that the Declaration is basically concerned with the provisions of the child's economic, psychological and social needs, hence the language is more appropriate in the field of child welfare.⁷³ That the contents of the declaration is skewed towards the social and economic welfare of children points to the fact that as at 1924, the modern development of civil and political right of children had not emerged.⁷⁴

The 1959 Declaration on the Rights of the Child built upon the little foundations of the 1924 Declaration, but expanded the rights. Built on 10 principles, the Declaration provides that "the child shall enjoy special protection," such that in the enactment of laws aimed at child protection and development, "the best interests of the child shall be the paramount consideration"⁷⁵. Public authorities are under duty to extend "particular care to children"⁷⁶ and the child must be protected against any form of neglect, cruelty and or exploitation. While the provisions of the Declarations are not binding, the fact that they have been unanimously adopted by states across the world accords it with some measure of force of law than ordinary UN General Assembly resolutions.

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, 1990

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child is the only comprehensive (covering civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights) and binding regional treaty focused on children's rights. It was adopted by the African Union to address perceived shortcomings in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, as the Convention does not fully reflect the specific realities of children in Africa. Similar to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child cannot be suspended in times of armed conflict. In addition, Article 22 obliges States to "respect and ensure respect for rules of international humanitarian law applicable in armed conflicts which affect the child" and "take all feasible measures to ensure the protection and care of children who are affected by armed conflicts". The Charter does not limit itself to international conflicts: "Such rules shall also apply to children in situations of internal armed conflicts, tension and strife"⁷⁷. Unlike the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the provisions of the African Charter apply to all children under the age of 18 years, including the provision on their recruitment and use in armed conflict: "States Parties to the present Charter shall take all necessary measures to ensure that no child shall take a direct part in hostilities and refrain in particular, from recruiting any child"⁷⁸. It

⁷¹ ICCPR, 1966 A. 24(1)(2)(3)

⁷² ICCPR, 1966 A. 4

⁷³ V. Bueren, International Law on the Right of the child. (Martinus Nijhoff publishes, 1998) 6.

⁷⁴ Ibid, P7

⁷⁵ Principle 2, Declaration on the Rights of the Child, 1959.

⁷⁶ Principle 6, Declaration on the Rights of the Child, 1959

⁷⁷ Article 22

⁷⁸ Article 22(2)

provided a launch pad for the adoption of various laws that would uphold the rights of children across African countries.

The Child Rights Act, 2003

In July, 2003, the Federal Republic of Nigeria enacted the Child Rights Act which, following the principles of the UN CRC, 1989 and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, 1989, sets out in clear terms, the rights and responsibilities of the Nigerian child as well a system of child justice administration⁷⁹. It defines a child as “a person under the age of eighteen years”⁸⁰. The Act is founded on the philosophy of the ‘best interest of the child’ to the effect that “in every action concerning a child, whether undertaken by an individual, public or private body, institutions or service, court of law, or administrative or legislative authority, the best interest of the child shall be the primary consideration”⁸¹. To that extent, not only must a child “be given such protection and care as is necessary for the well-being of the child, taking into account the rights and duties of the child’s parents, legal guardians, or other individuals, institutions, services, agencies, organizations or bodies legally responsible for the child”⁸² but also “every person, institution, service, agency, organization and body responsible for the care or protection of children shall conform with the standards established by the appropriate authorities, particularly in the areas of safety, health, welfare, number and suitability of their staff and competent supervision”⁸³. This basically confirms to the child protectionist model.

However, following the philosophy of the child liberationist model that sees children as right-bearing beings with agency, the Act specifically conferred specific rights as all the *fundamental rights* enshrined in Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria⁸⁴; the right to survival and development⁸⁵; right to a name⁸⁶; freedom of association and peaceful assembly⁸⁷; freedom of thought, conscience and religion⁸⁸; right to private and family life⁸⁹; right to freedom of movement⁹⁰; right to freedom from discrimination⁹¹; right to dignity of the child⁹²; right to leisure, recreation and cultural activities⁹³; right to health and heal services⁹⁴; right to parental care, protection and maintenance⁹⁵; right of child to free, compulsory and universal primary education⁹⁶; right of child in need of special protection measure⁹⁷; right of the unborn child to protection against harm⁹⁸ and the right to enter contracts for necessities⁹⁹. The Act also imposes responsibilities on children in relation to the child’s family, community, country and the international community¹⁰⁰.

With respect to the protection of children in armed conflict, the Act specially prohibits the recruitment of children into the armed force. It provides that No child shall be recruited into any of the branches of the armed forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2) The Government or any other relevant agency or body shall ensure that no child is directly involved in any military operation or hostilities.¹⁰¹ This accords with the internationally accepted standard for recruitment into the armed forces as applicable under prime principles of humanitarian and human rights law. Thus, by this Nigeria has

⁷⁹C. Amalu, Nigerian child and the Child Rights Act. *Vanguard*, June 29, 2010.

⁸⁰ Child Rights Act, 2003. S. 277.

⁸¹ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 1

⁸² Child Rights Act 2003, S. 2(1)

⁸³ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 2(2)

⁸⁴ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 3

⁸⁵ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 4

⁸⁶ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 5

⁸⁷ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 6

⁸⁸ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 7

⁸⁹ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 8

⁹⁰ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 9

⁹¹ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 10

⁹² Child Rights Act 2003, S. 11

⁹³ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 12

⁹⁴ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 13

⁹⁵ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 14

⁹⁶ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 15

⁹⁷ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 16

⁹⁸ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 17

⁹⁹ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 18

¹⁰⁰ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 19

¹⁰¹ Child Rights Act 2003, S. 34(1) & (2)

made it clear that it abides by international law principles and standards of recruitment that insists on 18 years and above.

While the Child Rights Act has been adopted in various parts of Nigeria, it has been noted however that it has failed to really protect Nigerian children from abuses in various forms¹⁰² and communal clashes and unlawful killings. According to a 2005 Report prepared for the Committee of the United Nations stated explicitly that:

Nigeria is often affected by bloody conflicts between different groups of the population. Most people simply refer to these clashes as communal and/or ethnic conflicts. But causes are numerous, and although they clearly include ethnic, social and cultural dimensions, a serious analysis shows that external political factors - such as control over resources (land, water, petrol, etc.) - also play an important role. Nigeria is often affected by bloody conflicts between different groups of the population. Most people simply refer to these clashes as communal and/or ethnic conflicts. But causes are numerous, and although they clearly include ethnic, social and cultural dimensions, a serious analysis shows that external political factors - such as control over resources (land, water, petrol, etc.) - also play an important role. The State Report submitted by Nigeria recognizes that “increased frequency of communal conflicts” has “occasioned the loss of [...] parents, abandonment, disabling injuries and in many more cases, loss of lives [for many children]”. It also comments some initiatives taken by NGOs to foster conflict resolution mechanisms and acknowledges the urgent need for “better emergency preparedness”¹⁸ in order to better protect children in this context, but fails to develop and explain in detail campaigns launched by the federal authorities. A report released by OMCT and CLEEN in 2002¹⁹ notes that - between the inauguration of the elected government in May 1999 and 2002 - the alarmingly high number of "over 50 outbreaks of targeted violence" have taken place in Nigeria. The report analyses the reasons and the consequences, as well as the "role of the State and its security agencies in fueling and participating in [...]" some of these “incidents of so-called intra or inter-communal, ethnic, religious or political conflicts.” Serious allegations were established that the government of Nigeria has not only failed to prevent communal conflicts, but that it has – in many cases – even contributed to the disastrous consequences of the conflicts. OMCT and CLEEN are deeply concerned by the fact that children have not been spared and many of them, including school children, have been killed during the conflicts. These killings cannot be considered as “causalities”, but clearly amount to unlawful killings for which the armed forces and the government of Nigeria must be held accountable. Often, such as in the case of Odi Killings, no difference has been made between children and adults and children have routinely been shot to death and burnt. Children from conflict regions also suffer from the loss of their parents, displacement and closure of schools and/or hospitals. Sometimes, such as during the Kaduna 2000 crisis, most of those arrested were children. They were detained in extremely poor hygienic conditions and many suffered different forms of ill-treatment.¹⁰³

The 2015 Report of the UN Secretary General¹⁰⁴ on *Children and Armed Conflict* states:

Increased reports were received on the recruitment and use of boys and girls by Boko Haram in support roles and in combat. Children were also used as human shields to protect Boko Haram elements. Another alarming trend observed since July was the growing number of girls used as suicide bombers in populated urban centres. For example, in July, four teenage girls were reported to have carried out a series of suicide attacks attributed to Boko Haram in Kano. A 13-year-old girl from Adamawa State was reportedly rescued at a checkpoint in Katsina State while carrying a belt with explosives. The United Nations also received reports

¹⁰²Akinwumi, Olayinka Silas (2009). Legal Impediments on the Practical Implementation of the Child Right Act (2003)(37)(3) *International Journal of Legal Information* 10.

¹⁰³ Committee on the Rights of the Child, *Rights of the Child in Nigeria: Report on the implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child by Nigeria*. Geneva, January 2005.

¹⁰⁴ Report of the UN Secretary General, *Children and armed conflict*, 5 June 2015, A/69/926-S/2015/409.

of children joining CJ¹⁰⁵TF and other vigilante groups, voluntarily or forcibly, and being used to man checkpoints, gather intelligence and participate in armed patrols. It was reported that some of the civilians, including children, who had voluntarily joined a particular side sometimes had done so in order to avoid the suspicion that they were associated with, or sympathetic to, the other side. The killing of civilians, including children, by Boko Haram continued and sharply increased during the period under review. It is estimated that at least 7,380 persons were killed in 255 incidents (5,083 in Borno, 893 in Adamawa, 517 in Yobe and 887 in other states). Data on the age and status of the victims is not available and therefore, the exact number of children killed and injured remains unknown. Children were killed and maimed during Boko Haram raids on villages, in targeted attacks in public places, in clashes between Boko Haram and the Nigerian security forces and as a result of suicide bombings. Children were also killed by Boko Haram in their schools. Education authorities in the north - east recorded the killing of 314 school children between January 2012 and December 2014. Children were killed and maimed during Boko Haram raids on villages, in targeted attacks in public places, in clashes between Boko Haram and the Nigerian security forces and as a result of suicide bombings. Children were also killed by Boko Haram in their schools. Education authorities in the north-east recorded the killing of 314 school children between January 2012 and December 2014. In February, 59 secondary schoolboys were shot or burned to death in their dormitory during a night-time attack in BuniYadi, Yobe. In November, a suicide bomber disguised in a school uniform killed at least 47 school children and injured 117 others in Potiskum, Yobe. In addition, 26 incidents of suicide attacks were reported, in the states of Borno (nine), Kano (eight), Yobe (five), Gombe (two), Bauchi (one), and in the Federal Capital Territory (one). The suicide attacks reportedly involved 45 suicide bombers and claimed the lives of at least 688 persons, including over 200 persons at the Grand Mosque in Kano. Since 2009, Boko Haram has reportedly been responsible for the abduction of at least 500 young women and girls from their homes or schools and while travelling on roads in the affected States. The abduction of 276 girls from their school in Chibok, Borno, in April 2014, represented the largest single incident of abduction attributed to the group. Of the 276 abductees, 57 managed to escape. Incidents continued to be reported and, in September, over 100 young women and girls were abducted from villages during attacks in Adamawa State. The whereabouts of the Chibok girls and the other abductees remain unknown. According to accounts from escapees, they were subjected to forcible religious conversion, physical and psychological abuse, forced labour and forced marriage to Boko Haram fighters. The group's stated motives for abductions include retaliation against the Government for detention of relatives and punishment of schoolchildren for attending Western-style schools.¹⁰⁶

It is thus obvious children are victims of the internal armed conflict between the Nigerian state and the Boko Haram Islamic terrorists.

The Nigerian Civil War

Nigeria became an independent country in 1960. A coup and counter-coup in 1966 triggered a massacre of Igbo living in the north, which prompted a secessionist movement in the eastern (predominantly Igbo) states. The subsequent Biafran war (1967–1970) resulted in around 75,000 battle-related deaths (BRDs) and the number of civilian deaths is estimated to be in the millions.¹⁰⁷ The Nigerian Civil War (1967–1970), also known as the Biafran War, remains one of the most significant and tragic episodes in Nigeria's history, with profound implications for the rights of vulnerable persons, particularly Children during armed conflict. This conflict offers a crucial historical lens through which to examine the challenges of protecting vulnerable children amidst internal armed conflict and has continued relevance to Nigeria's contemporary counter-terrorism and security operations.

¹⁰⁵ Civilian Joint Task Force

¹⁰⁶ Report of the UN Secretary General, *Children and armed conflict*, 5 June 2015, A/69/926-S/2015/409, paragraphs 232-236.

¹⁰⁷ A Jones and R Naylor, *The Quantitative impact of Armed Conflict on Education in Nigeria: Counting the Human and Financial costs* (CFBT Education Trust 2014) 5

The Nigerian Civil War erupted following the attempted secession of the Eastern Region as the Republic of Biafra. The war was marked by intense hostilities between the Nigerian federal government and Biafran secessionist forces. The conflict resulted in widespread humanitarian crises, including mass displacement, starvation, and civilian casualties. The war's scale and intensity meant that millions of civilians, including women, children, and the elderly—groups considered vulnerable under both international and national legal frameworks—suffered devastating consequences.

During the Nigerian Civil War, vulnerable Children were disproportionately affected in several ways. Millions of Children were forced to flee their homes, becoming internally displaced persons (IDPs) with limited access to basic necessities. Blockades and sieges imposed by federal forces led to widespread famine in Biafra, resulting in the deaths of hundreds of thousands, particularly children. Both sides faced accusations of targeting civilian populations, including the use of starvation as a weapon of war, which contravened principles of international humanitarian law. The war inflicted deep psychological scars on survivors, many of whom faced long-term deprivation and stigma. During the Nigerian civil war, the Nigerian Air Force pilots were particularly noteworthy for not respecting Geneva conventions resolutions describing civilian safe havens, such as hospitals, refugee and food distribution camps, and centers of religious worship, one European engaged in working on the Biafran side of the war front was seen carrying 117 dying children in his truck to a hospital in a single night.¹⁰⁸

The Nigerian Civil War predated much of the current international legal framework protecting vulnerable children during armed conflict, such as the Additional Protocols to the Geneva Conventions (1977). Nevertheless, basic humanitarian principles and customary international law governed conduct during the conflict. The war exposed critical gaps in the enforcement and respect of these principles, underscoring the need for stronger protections for vulnerable children during internal conflicts.

The Nigerian Civil War serves as a historical reference point illustrating the severe impact of armed conflict on vulnerable persons and the critical need for robust legal protections and humanitarian responses. Understanding this legacy is vital for shaping policies and operations that respect the rights and dignity of vulnerable groups during Nigeria's ongoing conflicts.

CONCLUSION

The examination of the legal protection of children in armed conflict has shown that while there are laudably ample provisions of international humanitarian, human rights and criminal law that seek to protect children in armed conflicts, there is however a wide gulf between the provisions of the law and practical realities. Thus, despite the provisions of these laws, children are still not only made victims of armed conflicts, but also made to play direct or indirect roles during armed conflict. This has been demonstrated not only in the Middle East, Europe, and the Americas, but also in different parts of Africa and Nigeria in particular. Efforts at protecting children in armed conflicts at family, community, state and international levels have failed to meet all desired goals of the law for children. While the international community, particularly, the United Nations and its organs and agencies as well as child rights advocacy organisations have made commendable efforts to protect children, there is however glaring evidence across the world that these efforts have only had minimal impacts. In Nigeria, this is the case because there is little or nothing proactive in terms of policy and positive steps by the Federal, State and local governments in the country to protect children during armed conflicts. That the government and its military personnel are not responsible for the killing, maiming, abduction, recruitment and use of children in armed conflict does not absolve the state of responsibility under international law. The law is long settled that a government is under a *responsibility to protect* its citizens from abuse by itself, but also from the positive acts of private persons and non-state actors. Proactive steps must thus be taken at all levels of government to protect children in armed conflict for children represent the future of the human race. Failing to protect children during armed conflict is a threat to the survival of the human family.

¹⁰⁸ C. Achebe, *There was a Country, A personal History of Biafra* (Penguin Books Ltd, 2012) 213

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the foregoing, it is hereby recommended thus:

1. There is need to amend and reinforce extant provisions of international humanitarian law to make same child-specific so as to accord children the maximum protection they deserve owing to their vulnerability during armed conflict. Provisions should be made for children *alone* which will make it clear and explicit during armed conflict that children are a *special* group of the civilian population who must be spared, protected and provided for during armed conflict by not only state actors, but also non-state actors.
2. Over and over the 'name and shame' strategy of the UN Security Council, the international community should employ a clearly more aggressive strategy by imposing targeted political and economic sanctions on states that fail to discharge its statutory and international responsibility to protect children during armed conflict.
3. Non-state individuals and groups like Boko Haram that target and employ the services of children during armed conflicts should not only be prosecuted before national and international criminal courts, but also be visited with travel restrictions, arms and commodity embargoes and diplomatic restrictions so as to not only dissuade same, but also punish for the crimes so committed. Amnesties should not be granted to anyone who is takes part in crimes against children in time of armed conflict.
4. More efforts should be made at the international level by regulating the flow of small arms and light weapons which are usually handy to child soldiers, while more aggressive steps should be taken by states at national level to mop up light weapons in circulation before and after any armed conflict.
5. Children who are accused of crimes allegedly committed while they were associated with rebels should be considered primarily as victims of offences, not only as perpetrators. These children must be treated in accordance with international law in a framework of restorative justice and social rehabilitation, consistent with international law. Any judicial proceedings involving child soldiers must be within a framework of restorative justice that guarantees the physical, psychological and social rehabilitation of the child.
6. While doing disarmament, demobilization and reintegration process, special provisions should be made for children. These should include special measures to ensure children's protection from exploitation and re-recruitment and address the special needs of girls and children with disabilities. Children should be given an opportunity to express themselves in the process.
7. Governments in Nigeria at all levels should work with the UN-Nigeria task force on children affected by armed conflict to monitor and report on violations against children which was established in 2014. This will enable the reports to have local inputs and enable governments at all levels to be fully cognizant of children affected during armed conflict as well easily spot violators of children's rights during hostilities.